

1 **Study of the influence of particle size of activate carbon**
2 **for the manufacture of electrodes for supercapacitors**

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4 Antonio Macías-García^{1*}, Diego Torrejón-Martín¹,
5 M^a Ángeles Díaz-Díez¹, Juan Pablo Carrasco-Amador²

6
7 ¹*Department of Mechanical, Energetic and Materials Engineering. School of industrial Engineering.*
8 *University of Extremadura. Avda. de Elvas, s/n, 06006, Badajoz. Spain*

9 ²*Department of Graphic Expression. School of industrial Engineering. University of Extremadura.*
10 *Avda. de Elvas, s/n, 06006, Badajoz. Spain*

11
12 **Abstract**

13 By a mechanical treatment of ball milling and from a commercial activate
14 carbon (CAC), four different samples, with different particle size between 200 nm and
15 1,3 mm, were obtained. These samples were chemically, texturally and morphologically
16 characterized. Likewise, the influence of the particle size on the electrical qualities of
17 the electrodes made for supercapacitors were studied. It was shown that milling process
18 improves, in all cases, the electrical qualities of the supercapacitor made with original
19 CAC. Nevertheless, it was observed that, from a certain particle size, due to particle
20 agglomeration, the electrical capacity of supercapacitors decreased. Carbon black
21 Vulcan 3 (V3) was used as mesoporous additive in order to improve the electrical
22 capacities. The electrical capacity of the samples studied increased between 6 and 221
23 %, in most cases, when V3 was used. In addition, we modelled and printed in 3D, the
24 central parts of the supercapacitors used in this study.

25
26 **Keywords:** Supercapacitors, energy storage, 3D printing, particle size, electrodes.

28 **1. Introduction**

29

30 Nowadays, the study of energy still remains the center of academic research, as well as of the
31 development of new techniques globally. The main reason is that the sources of fossil fuels are
32 not inexhaustible [1], [2], but there are other factors, such as global warming, or the exponential
33 growth of the world population, leading to the fact that the methods of energy storage acquire
34 more importance than ever. Among the energy storage devices supercapacitors are one of the
35 most interesting technologies. [3]

36

37 This article focuses on the manufacture of electrodes for electric double layer capacitors
38 (EDLCs), whose main advantages are its fast loading and unloading processes, its ability to
39 release large power peaks and its long service life (> 10⁶ cycles) [4]. The EDLCs are used in
40 numerous applications [4-9], among which the automotive in electric and hybrid vehicles are the
41 most notable ones.

42

43 Carbon materials, including carbon nanotubes, activated carbon (AC) [10], graphite, carbon
44 aerogels [11], carbon nanofibers [12], etc., have been extensively studied for the manufacture of
45 supercapacitation electrodes due to their large specific surface area, high conductivity and
46 chemical stability [13]. The specific surface and porosity are essential for their electrochemical
47 performance in supercapacitors [14]. Thus, an adequate distribution of micro and mesoporous
48 can improve the electrochemical performance of this type of materials [15].

49

50 One of the materials used to manufacture EDLCs are activated carbons (AC) [5]. AC have a
51 high specific surface area, chemical stability, good conductivity, charge accumulation capacity
52 at the electrode/electrolyte interface and low economic cost, compared to other materials used in
53 electrode production [1], [5], [16]. ACs are obtained from coal, products from biomass,
54 polymers, etc. [1], [17], [18].

55

56 In recent years, research in the field of nanocarbons, microcarbons, structured carbons have
57 increased, due to their excellent physical and chemical qualities [19], [20]. Thus, more and more
58 researchers use nanoparticles and microparticles in the manufacture of carbon electrodes for
59 supercapacitors. [21]

60

61 The disadvantage of these materials is the need to develop methods for large-scale
62 manufacturing, to be fast and cost-effective, without altering their exceptional properties.

63

64 The objective of this work is to reduce the particle size of a commercial activated carbon to the
65 nanometric or micrometric scale and to study its influence in the manufacture of electrodes for
66 supercapacitors.
67

68 **2. Materials and methods**

69

70 **2.1. Materials**

71 Commercial activated carbon (CAC) GMI 1.240-1/S provided by CPL GalaQuim Ltd was used
72 for the manufacture of the electrodes. Carbon black Vulcan 3 (V3) supplied by Carbot was
73 employed in order to improve the conductivity of the electrodes manufactured, and
74 polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) from the company Aldrich was used as a binding substance in
75 the manufacture of the electrodes.

76

77 **2.2. Procedure**

78 The CAC was subjected to a mechanical treatment in a ball mill during different time periods
79 (0, 10, 30 and 120 minutes), in order to reduce its particle size, generating the samples collected
80 in table 1. The CAC milling was carried out in a SPEX SamplePrep 8000D Mixer / Mill®
81 milled together with Tungsten carbide balls (WC) in a 1:10 ratio.

82

Sample	Milling time (min)
GMI 1.240	0
GMI 1.240-10	10
GMI 1.240-30	30
GMI 1.240-120	120

83

Table 1. Samples

84

85

86 GMI 1.240 is commercial activated carbon, GMI 1.240- t, are the carbons resulting from the
87 grinding time (10, 30 and 120 min). The images corresponding to scanning electron microscopy
88 Hitachi Microscope S-4800, were used to determine the particle size of the samples. For this
89 purpose, the images were divided into 16 quadrants, and four of them, randomly chosen, were
90 studied, as a way to obtain representative elements of the different particle sizes and their
91 standard deviation in each sample.

92

93 The textural characterization of the samples was made from the adsorption isotherms of N₂ at
94 -196 °C obtained by a QUANTACHROME AUTOSORB-1.

95

96 The electrical conductivity measurement (σ) was carried out in 0.08 g. sample, at room
97 temperature by impedance spectroscopy in a frequency range of 20-10⁶ Hz with a voltage of 1V
98 on a Precision LCR Meter (QuadTech, model 1920).

99

100 Infrared spectroscopy with Fourier transform (FT-IR) was performed on a Perkin Elmer
101 spectrometer, model 1720, between 400 and 4000 cm⁻¹.

102

103 The surface characterization of the samples was made by SEM, performed on a Hitachi
104 Microscope S-4800, to study its morphology and agglomeration degree. From the characterized
105 samples, eight electrodes, whose composition is shown in table 2, were manufactured.

106

	GMI 1240		GMI 1240-10		GMI 1240-30		GMI 1240-120	
	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8
CA (%)	86.30	80.87	86.50	80.74	86.50	81.07	86.40	80.87
V3 (%)	0	5.68	0	5.68	0	5.55	0	5.68
PVDF (%)	13.70	13.45	13.50	13.58	13.50	13.38	13.60	13.45

107

Table 2. Electrodes composition

108

109 For the manufacture of the electrodes, the different components were mixed in an agate
110 mortar. 0.1 g. of the total blend was taken and pressed into a titanium mold for 3 minutes, at
111 100 bar, in a CARVER uniaxial press model #3912. 100 bar pressure in the fabrication
112 process of all prepared electrodes increases electrical conductivity and compaction.

113

114 Each apparatus was previously calibrated, using standard patterns.

115 The central part of the Swagelok cell was designed with Inventor® CAD software that allows
116 mechanical design and 3D simulation and then printed in 3D using fused filament fabrication.
117 Swagelok type electrochemical cells with configuration of two electrodes in the form of
118 opposing discs have been used for the study of supercapacitors. The supercapacitors were
119 formed by the aforementioned electrodes, an 0.5 M H₂SO₄ aqueous electrolyte, and glass
120 fiber as a separating material. In order to study the behavior of the designed supercapacitors,
121 both R and C were measured in a frequency range of 20-10⁶ Hz, being examined at voltages
122 of 0.2, 0.5 and 0.8 V. Precision LCR Meter (QuadTech, model 1920) measuring equipment
123 was used.

124

125 **3. Results and discussion**

126

127 **3.1. Mechanical treatment**

128 The measured particle sizes are shown in table 3. As it can be seen in table 3, particle sizes vary
129 between 1220 μm and 430 nm, in the micrometric-nanometric range.

130

Sample	Particle size		Standard deviation	
GMI 1.240	1220 μm		0.254	
GMI 1.240-10	2.040 μm	8.870 μm	0.660	7.210
GMI 1.240-30	0.610 μm	2.050 μm	0.200	0.830
GMI 1.240-120	0.430 μm	1.790 μm	0.200	0.670

131

Table 3. Particle sizes

132

133 As shown in figures 4 (a-d), as the milling time increases, the smaller particles (approximately
134 430 nm) undergo an agglomeration phenomenon around the larger particles, showing a
135 heterogeneous distribution of particle size, and increasing intraparticle porosity.

136

137 **3.2. Textural Characterization**

138 From the adsorption isotherms of N_2 at -196°C (figure 1), the porous texture of the samples
139 was determined. Their values are represented in table 4.

140

Figure 1. Adsorption isotherms of N₂ at -196°C.

141

142

143

144 After having observed figure 1, the isotherms can be classified as type II isotherms, according to
 145 the BDDT classification [22]. All samples show an open elbow at low relative pressures,
 146 characteristic behavior of mesoporous solids. Likewise, the samples have a plateau with a slight
 147 upward slope at high relative pressures, characteristic behavior of the existence of mesoporous
 148 structures. Table 4 data shows that as the milling time increases, the BET surface of the samples
 149 decreases, GMI 1.240 > GMI 1.240-10 > GMI 1.240-30 > GMI 1.240-120. This fact can be
 150 explained by the destruction of part of the internal porous structure of the material in the
 151 milling. This table confirms that the samples are mainly microporous with a slight mesoporous
 152 development.

153

SAMPLE	SBET (m ² ·g ⁻¹)	Vmi (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹)	Vme (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹)
GMI 1.240	878.00	0.402	0.095
GMI 1.240-10	806.95	0.366	0.087
GMI 1.240-30	708.65	0.327	0.078
GMI 1.240-120	472.00	0.221	0.064

Table 4. Textural data of the samples

154

155

156 The pore size distribution was determined by the DFT method (figure 2). Figure 2 shows that
 157 all the samples have a unimodal distribution, in which the micropores of approximately 5 Å

158 predominate. This behavior agrees with the elbows observed in the adsorption isotherms (figure
159 1). Figure 3 contains the data provided by the BJH method to determine the distribution of
160 narrow mesopores. As it has been shown, there is evidence of narrow mesopores ($<30\text{\AA}$). The
161 behavior was similar for all samples.
162

163
164

Figure 2. Pore size distribution by DFT method.

165
166
167
168

Figure 3. Narrow mesopore size distribution by BJH method.

169 **3.3. Analysis of functional groups**

170 The analysis of functional groups was performed only on the activated carbon GMI 1.240, since
171 surface functional groups are not modified with mechanical treatment. The spectral range 1800-
172 600 cm^{-1} has been represented as the range corresponding to the most interesting functional
173 groups of an activated carbon. The band of approximately 1635 cm^{-1} corresponds to absorbed
174 water that usually appears in the range of 1700 to 1600 cm^{-1} . The 1556 cm^{-1} band is attributed to
175 the voltage vibration of the double bond $\text{C} = \text{C}$ of aromatic rings, that usually appears in the
176 range of 1600 to 1500 cm^{-1} with varying intensity. The 1093 cm^{-1} band is attributed to flexural
177 vibrations in the plane of C-H bond of aromatic rings that give rise to absorptions between 1275
178 and 960 cm^{-1} . The 796 cm^{-1} and 688 cm^{-1} bands are attributed to out-of-plane flexion vibrations
179 of the C-H bond of aromatic rings typically occurring in the range of 900-690 cm^{-1} .

180

181 **3.4. Morphological analysis**

182 The morphology of the samples has been studied by SEM (figures 4, a-d). They show how as
183 the grinding time increases, the particle size decreases. The sizes obtained range from 1220 μm ,
184 of the unmilled sample (GMI 1.240), to particles of approximately 430 nm (GMI 1.240-120).
185 It is also observed that in a same sample there is a heterogeneous distribution of particle size.
186 This can be found in sample GMI 1.240-120, where a multitude of small particles
187 (approximately 300 nm) coexist with larger particles (2500 nm). What causes a phenomenon of
188 agglomeration of the smaller particles.

189

191

192 **Figure 4.** SEM of samples GMI 1.240 (a), GMI 1.240-10 (b), GMI 1.240-30 (c) and GMI 1.240-120 (d)
 193 respectively.

194

195

196 **3.5. Conductivity**

197 Figure 5 shows the variation of electrical conductivity of samples with the pressure, during the
 198 compaction process. The results shown in the figure 5 reveal that as the grinding time increases
 199 (smaller particle sizes), the conductivity decreases. This fact can be attributed to the increase of
 200 the intraparticle porosity, as seen in chapter 3.1. and as it is presented in the figures 4.

Figure 5. Electrical conductivity variation of the samples with the pressure during the compaction process.

For other researchers, the importance of mesoporous structure [23][24], chemical surface [25], physical and chemical properties [18-21], textural properties [27], etc., have a great influence on electrical properties of activated carbon.

3.6. Supercapacitors

In this chapter of the article, the study of prepared electrodes and their application to supercapacitors are addressed. For this purpose, we analyze the influence of their composition, the electrolyte type and the concentration, and the voltage to which the different supercapacitors are subjected.

The Activated Carbons are materials of great interest to be used as electrodes in supercapacitors, due to their physical and chemical qualities combination, which were detailed addressed in the introduction of this article.

The cell voltage is determined by the electrochemical stability of the electrolyte used. For aqueous electrolytes, the work potential cannot be higher than 1 V, because above that value electrolysis takes place. Aqueous electrolytes usually present a higher ionic conductivity, 0.8 S cm⁻¹ for the H₂SO₄, versus lower values for organic electrolytes and a lower cost, from an economic point of view [28]. Other aspects to bear in mind when selecting an electrolyte are: the corrosive effects that can provoke the dissolution over the cell components, and the size of the ions solvating, as it can be happening that all the surface of the material of the electrode is

226 not accessible. The electrolyte concentration should be high enough to avoid its depletion.
227 Already carried out research has shown that higher than 0.2M electrolyte concentrations are
228 enough [29]. The supercapacitors resistance is highly influenced by the electrolyte resistivity
229 and by the ions size that disseminate from the electrolyte to the pores of the electrode material.
230 This does not mean a problem in the case of aqueous electrolytes as KOH or H₂SO₄, but it does,
231 in the case of organic electrolytes, due to the higher size of their ions [30].

232

233 As for the study of the influence of the porous texture, because the first sample GMI 1.240,
234 subjected to different milling processes and according to the figures 2 and 3, changes in its
235 porous structure from the studies with DFT and BJH addressed in previous chapters are not
236 observed. Nevertheless, some authors note that the sudden decrease in the specific capacity of
237 activated carbons with the voltage is related to the samples microporosity, due to the slow
238 diffusion of the ions to the pores [31], something that could justify the low capacity of the first
239 sample GMI 1.240.

240

241 **Study of the influence on carbon black and particle size**

242

243 Two series of supercapacitors were carried away. The first one with V3 as a material providing
244 mesopores, and the second one that only had CAC and PVDF. The measurement of
245 supercapacitors electrical qualities was made as specified in the chapter 2.2.

246

247

248

248 **Figure 6.** Samples not containing V3 in their composition tested at 0,5 V.

249

250 As seen in the figure 6, it can be observed that the milling improves the capacity of the original
251 sample in approximately 569%, 405% and 273% (GMI 1.240-10, GMI 1.240-30 and GMI
252 1.240-120 samples respectively). However, after reaching a maximum, the capacity starts
253 decreasing.

254

255

256 **Figure 7.** Samples containing V3 in their composition tested at 0,5 V.

257

258 The purpose of these two series (figures 6 and 7) is verifying if the presence of carbon black V3
259 in the electrodes composition, notably improves its electrical capacity. The possible
260 improvement could be due to the fact that, structurally, carbon black V3 is mesoporous, in a
261 way that favors a quick propagation of the charge in a brief period of time. This effect is clearly
262 shown in the comparison of figures 6 and 7 where the samples GMI 1.240-120-V3 > GMI
263 1.240-120, GMI 1.240-30-V3 > GMI-1.240-30 y GMI-1.240-V3 > GMI 1.240 improve their
264 electrical capacity in a 66.09%, 6.47% and 221.79% respectively.

265

266 However, in the sample GMI 1.240-10 V3 < GMI 1.240-10 the process reverses. This can be
267 due to the fact that the particle size of the sample GMI-1.240-10 (2.04 μm – 8.87 μm) and of the
268 V3, drastically reduce its superficial area, as well as its mechanical resistance. Finally, the
269 percentage of carbon black present in the electrode, versus the particle size of the carbon black,
270 is rendered in the fact that there is a higher number of repulsion electrostatic interactions that
271 provoke that the electrode separated, deducting a considerable mechanical resistance and
272 electrical capacity. Meanwhile in the rest of the samples it can be observed that the electrode
273 presents a wide contact surface that allows a higher capacity of charge storing (figure 4). After
274 having seen this effect, it remains crucial to reach a balance between the contribution of particle

275 size of activated carbon, and the quantity of activated carbon added to the electrode.
276 Experimentally, it has been proved that adding carbon black in a proportion between the 5 and 6
277 % of the electrode mass, satisfies the balance between the increase of the electrical capacity and
278 the loss of mechanical resistance in the electrode. This has allowed the development of stable
279 and homogeneous electrodes, that present the desired behavior, as they are introduced within the
280 fold of the electrolyte dissolution [32].

281

282 On the other hand, both series present a similar behavior, having higher electric capacity values
283 at low frequencies, as it is shown in figures 6 and 7. In order to know the influence of voltage in
284 electrical capacity, a measurement of the capacity of each sample at voltage 0.2, 0.5 and 0.8 V
285 has been carried out, as shown in the figures 8-11.

286

287

288 **Figure 8.** Comparison of GMI 1.240 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

289

290

291

292

Figure 9. Comparison of GMI 1.240-10 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0.2, 0.5 and 0.8 V.

293

294

295

Figure 10. Comparison of GMI 1.240-30 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0.2, 0.5 and 0.8 V.

Figure 11. Comparison of GMI 1.240-120 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0.2, 0.5 and 0.8 V.

296

297

298

299

300 Having seen figures from 8 to 11, it is clearly observed that prepared samples, both with V3 and
 301 without it, present a higher electrical capacity for 0.5 V voltage. This process can be due to the
 302 fact that voltage favors a better dissociation of the electrolyte and, in this way, facilitates the
 303 diffusion of the ions to the surface and to the pores of the samples that are object of this study.
 304 At low potentials of 0.2V, this dissociation process of sulfuric acid occurs with a lower
 305 intensity, something that explains the low results of the electrical capacity of the sample, as the
 306 mobility of the ions is reduced.

307

308 On the other hand, it can be expected that at 0.8V voltages, the supercapacitors electrical
 309 capacity was higher. However, it is not the case, and this can be because of a possible
 310 competition among the ions to occupy the active centers between the ions coming from the
 311 sulfuric acid, and the ones originated from the possible starting of the water electrolysis.

312

313 4. Conclusions

314

315 In short, with this article it has been proved that the increase of the supercapacitor capacity not
 316 only depends on the porosity, the pore distribution, the BET surface or the electrical
 317 conductivity, but also on the particle size, as the smaller particles see their surface increase and
 318 the contact among them benefits the electrical charge storage. The mechanical treatment to
 319 reduce the size particle, only exerts influence on the supercapacitor capacity in a limited amount
 320 of milling time (10 minutes), decreasing the capacity of supercapacitors for particle sizes

321 corresponding to longer milling periods and smaller sizes of particles, probably due to a particle
322 agglomeration, and therefore decrease of the contact surface and increase of the interparticle
323 porosity.

324

325 The milling of CAC improves the electrical capacity in all cases between a 273% and a 569%,
326 as far as the GMI 1.240 is concerned, reaching a maximum after which the measurement that
327 increases the milling time of the CA, decreases the supercapacitor capacity. The reason may be
328 the agglomeration of the smaller particles as it is shown in figure 4. This fact can be solved with
329 the addition of V3. Other authors that have used this technique to reduce the size particle, have
330 experimented that the more the milling time, the lower the supercapacitor capacity [22-23],[34].
331 They believe that this fact is due to the mismatch produced in the size of the CA particles, as
332 well to the additive used to improve its conductivity, and they solve it milling the additive
333 together with the CA, something that can remain a new line of study for this project. The
334 milling of the initial AC, V3 and PVDF could be a good solution to reduce the presence of a
335 high interparticle porosity that affects the electrical capacity of the supercapacitor.

336

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432 **Table headings**

433 **Table 1.** Samples

434 **Table 2.** Electrodes composition

435 **Table 3.** Particle sizes

436 **Table 4.** Textural data of the samples

437 **Figure captions**

438 **Figure 1.** Adsorption isotherms of N₂ at -196°C.

439 **Figure 2.** Pore size distribution by DFT method.

440 **Figure 3.** Narrow mesopore size distribution by BJH method.

441 **Figure 4.** SEM of samples GMI 1.240 (a), GMI 1.240-10 (b), GMI 1.240-30 (c) and GMI 1.240-120 (d)
442 respectively.

443 **Figure 5.** Electrical conductivity variation of the samples with the pressure during the compaction
444 process.

445 **Figure 6.** Samples not containing V3 in their composition tested at 0,5 V.

446 **Figure 7.** Samples containing V3 in their composition tested at 0,5 V.

447 **Figure 8.** Comparison of GMI 1.240 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

448 **Figure 9.** Comparison of GMI 1.240-10 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8
449 V.

450 **Figure 10.** Comparison of GMI 1.240-30 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and
451 0,8 V.

452 **Figure 11.** Comparison of GMI 1.240-120 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and
453 0,8 V.

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Antonio Macías García, PhD
School of Industrial Engineering
University of Extremadura
Avda. de Elvas, s/n.
06006. Badajoz (Spain)
amacgar@unex.es

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Highlights:

- The increase of the capacity of the supercapacitors depends on the particle size.
- When the smaller particles increase, the storage of electrical charge increase.
- Reduce the size particle only exerts influence in a limited amount of milling time.
- Above that time, with smaller particle sizes, the capacity decreases.

Best regards,

Antonio Macías-García, PhD
University of Extremadura

Study of the influence of particle size of activate carbon for the manufacture of electrodes for supercapacitors

Antonio Macías-García^{1*}, Diego Torrejón-Martín¹,
M^a Ángeles Díaz-Díez¹, Juan Pablo Carrasco-Amador²

¹*Department of Mechanical, Energetic and Materials Engineering. School of industrial Engineering.
University of Extremadura. Avda. de Elvas, s/n, 06006, Badajoz. Spain*

²*Department of Graphic Expression. School of industrial Engineering. University of Extremadura.
Avda. de Elvas, s/n, 06006, Badajoz. Spain*

Abstract

By a mechanical treatment of ball milling and from a commercial activate carbon (CAC), four different samples, with different particle size between 200 nm and 1,3 mm, were obtained. These samples were chemically, texturally and morphologically characterized. Likewise, the influence of the particle size on the electrical qualities of the electrodes made for supercapacitors were studied. It was shown that milling process improves, in all cases, the electrical qualities of the supercapacitor made with original CAC. Nevertheless, it was observed that, from a certain particle size, due to particle agglomeration, the electrical capacity of supercapacitors decreased. Carbon black Vulcan 3 (V3) was used as mesoporous additive in order to improve the electrical capacities. The electrical capacity of the samples studied increased between 6 and 221 %, in most cases, when V3 was used. In addition, we modelled and printed in 3D, the central parts of the supercapacitors used in this study.

Keywords: Supercapacitors, energy storage, 3D printing, particle size, electrodes.

*Corresponding author:

E-mail address: amacgar@unex.es (Antonio Macías- García)

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the study of energy still remains the center of academic research, as well as of the development of new techniques globally. The main reason is that the sources of fossil fuels are not inexhaustible [1], [2], but there are other factors, such as global warming, or the exponential growth of the world population, leading to the fact that the methods of energy storage acquire more importance than ever. Among the energy storage devices supercapacitors are one of the most interesting technologies.

This article focuses on the manufacture of electrodes for electric double layer capacitors (EDLCs), whose main advantages are its fast loading and unloading processes, its ability to release large power peaks and its long service life ($> 10^6$ cycles) [3]. The EDLCs are used in numerous applications [4-8], among which the automotive in electric and hybrid vehicles are the most notable ones.

One of the materials used to manufacture EDLCs are activated carbons (AC) [4]. AC have a high specific surface area, chemical stability, good conductivity, charge accumulation capacity at the electrode/electrolyte interface and low economic cost, compared to other materials used in electrode production [1], [4], [9]. ACs are obtained from coal, products from biomass, polymers, etc. [1], [10], [11].

In recent years, research in the field of nanocarbons has increased, due to their excellent physical and chemical qualities [12], [13]. The disadvantage of these materials is the need to develop methods for large-scale manufacturing, to be fast and cost-effective, without altering their exceptional properties.

The objective of this work is to reduce the particle size of a commercial activated carbon to the nanometric scale and to study its influence in the manufacture of electrodes for supercapacitors.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Commercial activated carbon (CAC) GMI 1240-1/S provided by CPL GalaQuim Ltd was used for the manufacture of the electrodes. Carbon black Vulcan 3 (V3) supplied by Carbot was employed in order to improve the conductivity of the electrodes manufactured, and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) from the company Aldrich was used as a binding substance in the manufacture of the electrodes.

2.2. Procedure

The CAC was subjected to a mechanical treatment in a ball mill during different time periods (0, 10, 30 and 120 minutes), in order to reduce its particle size, generating the samples collected in table 1. The CAC milling was carried out in a SPEX SamplePrep 8000D Mixer / Mill® milled together with Tungsten carbide balls (WC) in a 1:10 ratio.

Sample	Milling time (min)
GMI 1.240	0
GMI 1.240-10	10
GMI 1.240-30	30
GMI 1.240-120	120

Table 1. Samples

The images corresponding to scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were used to determine the particle size of the samples. For this purpose, the images were divided into 16 quadrants, and four of them, randomly chosen, were studied, as a way to obtain representative elements of the different particle sizes and their standard deviation in each sample.

The textural characterization of the samples was made from the adsorption isotherms of N₂ at -196 °C obtained by a QUANTACHROME AUTOSORB-1.

The electrical conductivity measurement (σ) was carried out in 0,08 g. sample, at room temperature by impedance spectroscopy in a frequency range of 20-10⁶ Hz with a voltage of 1V on a Precision LCR Meter (QuadTech, model 1920).

Infrared spectroscopy with Fourier transform (FT-IR) was performed on a Perkin Elmer spectrometer, model 1720, between 400 and 4.000 cm^{-1} .

The surface characterization of the samples was made by SEM, performed on a Hitachi Microscope S-4800, to study its morphology and agglomeration degree. From the characterized samples, eight electrodes, whose composition is shown in table 2, were manufactured.

	GMI 1240		GMI 1240-10		GMI 1240-30		GMI 1240-120	
	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8
CA (%)	86,30	80,87	86,50	80,74	86,50	81,07	86,40	80,87
V3 (%)	0	5,68	0	5,68	0	5,55	0	5,68
PVDF (%)	13,70	13,45	13,50	13,58	13,50	13,38	13,60	13,45

Table 2. Electrodes composition

For the manufacture of the electrodes, the different components were mixed in an agate mortar. 0,1 g. of the total blend was taken and pressed into a titanium mold for 3 minutes, at 100 bar, in a CARVER uniaxial press model #3912.

Swagelok type electrochemical cells with configuration of two electrodes in the form of opposing discs have been used for the study of supercapacitors. The supercapacitors were formed by the aforementioned electrodes, an 0,5 M H_2SO_4 aqueous electrolyte, and glass fiber as a separating material. In order to study the behavior of the designed supercapacitors, both R and C were measured in a frequency range of 20-10⁶ Hz, being examined at voltages of 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V. Precision LCR Meter (QuadTech, model 1920) measuring equipment was used.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Mechanical treatment

The measured particle sizes are shown in table 3. As it can be seen in table 3, particle sizes vary between 1200 μm and 430 nm, in the micrometric-nanometric range.

Sample	Particle size		Standard deviation	
GMI 1.240	1.220 μm		0,254	
GMI 1.230-10	2,04 μm	8,87 μm	0,66	7,21

GMI 1.240-30	0,610 μm	2.050 μm	0,2	0,83
GMI 1.240-120	0,430 μm	1.790 μm	0,20	0,67

Table 3. Particle sizes

As shown in figures 4 (a-d), as the milling time increases, the smaller particles (approximately 430 nm) undergo an agglomeration phenomenon around the larger particles, showing a heterogeneous distribution of particle size, and increasing intraparticle porosity.

3.2. Textural Characterization

From the adsorption isotherms of N₂ at -196 ° C (figure 1), the porous texture of the samples was determined. Their values are represented in table 4.

Figure 1. Adsorption isotherms of N₂ at -196°C.

After having observed figure 1, the isotherms can be classified as type II isotherms, according to the BDDT classification [14]. All samples show an open elbow at low relative pressures, characteristic behavior of mesoporous solids. Likewise, the samples have a plateau with a slight upward slope at high relative pressures, characteristic behavior of the existence of mesoporous structures. Table 1 data shows that as the milling time increases, the BET surface of the samples decreases, GMI 1.240 > GMI 1.240-10 > GMI 1.240-30 > GMI 1.240-120. This fact can be explained by the destruction of part of the internal porous structure of the material in the milling.

This table confirms that the samples are mainly microporous with a slight mesoporous development.

SAMPLE	SBET ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	Vmi ($\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	Vme ($\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)
GMI 1.240	878,00	0,402	0,095
GMI 1.240-10	806,95	0,366	0,087
GMI 1.240-30	708,65	0,327	0,078
GMI 1.240-120	472,00	0,221	0,064

Table 4. Textural data of the samples

The pore size distribution was determined by the DFT method (figure 2). Figure 2 shows that all the samples have a unimodal distribution, in which the micropores of approximately 5 Å predominate. This behavior agrees with the elbows observed in the adsorption isotherms (figure 1). Figure 3 contains the data provided by the BJH method to determine the distribution of narrow mesopores. As it has been shown, there is evidence of narrow mesopores (<30Å). The behavior was similar for all samples.

Figure 2. Pore size distribution by DFT method.

Figure 3. Narrow mesopore size distribution by BJH method.

3.3. Analysis of functional groups

The analysis of functional groups was performed only on the activated carbon GMI 1.240, since surface functional groups are not modified with mechanical treatment. The spectral range $1.800\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been represented as the range corresponding to the most interesting functional groups of an activated carbon. The band of approximately 1.635 cm^{-1} corresponds to absorbed water that usually appears in the range of $1.700\text{ to }1.600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The 1.556 cm^{-1} band is attributed to the valence vibration of the double bond $\text{C}=\text{C}$ of aromatic rings, that usually appears in the range of $1.600\text{ to }1.500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with varying intensity. The 1.093 cm^{-1} band is attributed to flexural vibrations in the plane of C-H bond of aromatic rings that give rise to absorptions between $1.275\text{ and }960\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The 796 cm^{-1} and 688 cm^{-1} bands are attributed to out-of-plane flexion vibrations of the C-H bond of aromatic rings typically occurring in the range of $900\text{--}690\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

3.4. Morphological analysis

The morphology of the samples has been studied by SEM (figures 4, a-d). They show how as the grinding time increases, the particle size decreases. The sizes obtained range from $1.220\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, of the unmilled sample (GMI 1.240), to particles of approximately 430 nm (GMI 1.240-120). It is also observed that in a same sample there is a heterogeneous distribution of particle size. This can be found in sample GMI 1.240-120, where a multitude of small particles (approximately 300 nm)

coexist with larger particles (2.500 nm). What causes a phenomenon of agglomeration of the smaller particles.

Figure 4. SEM of samples GMI 1.240 (a), GMI 1.240-10 (b), GMI 1.240-30 (c) and GMI 1.240-120 (d) respectively.

3.5. Conductivity

Figure 5 shows the variation of electrical conductivity of samples with the pressure, during the compaction process. The results shown in the table reveal that as the grinding time increases (smaller particle sizes), the conductivity decreases. This fact can be attributed to the increase of the intraparticle porosity, as seen in chapter 3.1. and as it is presented in the figures 4.

Figure 5. Electrical conductivity variation of the samples with the pressure during the compaction process.

For other researchers, the importance of mesoporous structure [15][16], chemical surface [17], physical and chemical properties [18-21], textural properties [22], etc., have a great influence on electrical properties of activated carbon.

3.6. Supercapacitors

In this chapter of the article, the study of prepared electrodes and their application to supercapacitors are addressed. For this purpose, we analyze the influence of their composition, the electrolyte type and the concentration, and the voltage to which the different supercapacitors are subjected.

The Activated Carbons are materials of great interest to be used as electrodes in supercapacitors, due to their physical and chemical qualities combination, which were detailed addressed in the introduction of this article.

The cell voltage is determined by the electrochemical stability of the electrolyte used. For aqueous electrolytes, the work potential cannot be higher than 1 V, because above that value electrolysis takes place. Aqueous electrolytes usually present a higher ionic conductivity, 0,8 S cm⁻¹ for the H₂SO₄, versus lower values for organic electrolytes and a lower cost, from an economic point of view [23]. Other aspects to bear in mind when selecting an electrolyte are: the corrosive effects that can provoke the dissolution over the cell components, and the size of the ions solvating, as it can be happening that all the surface of the material of the electrode is not accessible. The

electrolyte concentration should be high enough to avoid its depletion. Already carried out research has shown that higher than 0,2M electrolyte concentrations are enough [24]. The supercapacitors resistance is highly influenced by the electrolyte resistivity and by the ions size that disseminate from the electrolyte to the pores of the electrode material. This does not mean a problem in the case of aqueous electrolytes as KOH or H₂SO₄, but it does, in the case of organic electrolytes, due to the higher size of their ions [25].

As for the study of the influence of the porous texture, because the first sample GMI 1.240, subjected to different milling processes and according to the figures 2 and 3, changes in its porous structure from the studies with DFT and BJH addressed in previous chapters are not observed. Nevertheless, some authors note that the sudden decrease in the specific capacity of activated carbons with the voltage is related to the samples microporosity, due to the slow diffusion of the ions to the pores [26], something that could justify the low capacity of the first sample GMI 1.240.

Study of the influence on carbon black and particle size

Two series of supercapacitors were carried away. The first one with V3 as a material providing mesopores, and the second one that only had CAC and PVDF. The measurement of supercapacitors electrical qualities was made as specified in the chapter 2.2.

Figure 6. Samples not containing V3 in their composition tested at 0,5 V.

As seen in the figure 6, it can be observed that the milling improves the capacity of the original sample in approximately 569%, 405% and 273% (GMI 1.240-10, GMI 1.240-30 and GMI 1.240-120 samples respectively). However, after reaching a maximum, the capacity starts decreasing.

Figure 7. Samples containing V3 in their composition tested at 0,5 V.

The purpose of these two series (figures 6 and 7) is verifying if the presence of carbon black V3 in the electrodes composition, notably improves its electrical capacity. The possible improvement could be due to the fact that, structurally, carbon black V3 is mesoporous, in a way that favors a quick propagation of the charge in a brief period of time. This effect is clearly shown in the comparison of figures 6 and 7 where the samples GMI 1.240-120-V3 > GMI 1.240-120, GMI 1.240-30-V3 > GMI-1.240-30 y GMI-1.240-V3 > GMI 1.240 improve their electrical capacity in a 66,09%, 6,47% and 221,79% respectively.

However, in the sample GMI 1.240-10 V3 < GMI 1.240-10 the process reverses. This can be due to the fact that the particle size of the sample GMI-1.240-10 (2,04 μm – 8,87 μm) and of the V3, drastically reduce its superficial area, as well as its mechanical resistance. Finally, the percentage of carbon black present in the electrode, versus the particle size of the carbon black, is rendered in the fact that there is a higher number of repulsion electrostatic interactions that provoke that the electrode separated, deducting a considerable mechanical resistance and electrical capacity. Meanwhile in the rest of the samples it can be observed that the electrode presents a wide contact surface that allows a higher capacity of charge storing (figure 4). After having seen this effect, it remains crucial to reach a balance between the contribution of particle size of activated carbon, and the quantity of activated carbon added to the electrode. Experimentally, it has been proved

that adding carbon black in a proportion between the 5 and 6 % of the electrode mass, satisfies the balance between the increase of the electrical capacity and the loss of mechanical resistance in the electrode. This has allowed the development of stable and homogeneous electrodes, that present the desired behavior, as they are introduced within the fold of the electrolyte dissolution [27].

On the other hand, both series present a similar behavior, having higher electric capacity values at low frequencies, as it is shown in figures 6 and 7. In order to know the influence of voltage in electrical capacity, a measurement of the capacity of each sample at voltage 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V has been carried out, as shown in the figures 8-11.

Figure 8. Comparison of GMI 1.240 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

Figure 9. Comparison of GMI 1.240-10 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

Figure 10. Comparison of GMI 1.240-30 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

Figure 11. Comparison of GMI 1.240-120 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

Having seen figures from 8 to 11, it is clearly observed that prepared samples, both with V3 and without it, present a higher electrical capacity for 0,5 V voltage. This process can be due to the fact that voltage favors a better dissociation of the electrolyte and, in this way, facilitates the diffusion of the ions to the surface and to the pores of the samples that are object of this study. At low potentials of 0,2V, this dissociation process of sulfuric acid occurs with a lower intensity, something that explains the low results of the electrical capacity of the sample, as the mobility of the ions is reduced.

On the other hand, it can be expected that at 0,8V voltages, the supercapacitors electrical capacity was higher. However, it is not the case, and this can be because of a possible competition among the ions to occupy the active centers between the ions coming from the sulfuric acid, and the ones originated from the possible starting of the water electrolysis.

4. Conclusions

In short, with this article it has been proved that the increase of the supercapacitor capacity not only depends on the porosity, the pore distribution, or the electrical conductivity, but also on the particle size, as the smaller particles see their surface increase and the contact among them benefits the electrical charge storage. The mechanical treatment to reduce the size particle, only exerts influence on the supercapacitor capacity in a limited amount of milling time (10 minutes),

decreasing the capacity of supercapacitors for particle sizes corresponding to longer milling periods and smaller sizes of particles, probably due to a particle agglomeration.

The milling of CAC improves the electrical capacity in all cases between a 273% and a 569%, as far as the GMI 1.240 is concerned, reaching a maximum after which the measurement that increases the milling time of the CA, decreases the supercapacitor capacity. The reason may be the agglomeration of the smaller particles as it is shown in figure 4. This fact can be solved with the addition of V3. Other authors that have used this technique to reduce the size particle, have experimented that the more the milling time, the lower the supercapacitor capacity [22-23],[29]. They believe that this fact is due to the mismatch produced in the size of the CA particles, as well to the additive used to improve its conductivity, and they solve it milling the additive together with the CA, something that can remain a new line of study for this project.

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Figure 7. Samples containing V3 in their composition tested at 0,5 V.

Figure 8. Comparison of GMI 1.240 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

Figure 9. Comparison of GMI 1.240-10 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

Figure 10. Comparison of GMI 1.240-30 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

Figure 11. Comparison of GMI 1.240-120 samples not containing V3 and containing V3 at 0,2, 0,5 and 0,8 V.

Adsorption isotherms

DFT Method

BJH Method

Voltages comparison

Voltajes comparision GMI 1240-10

Voltages comparison GMI 1240-30

Voltages comparison GMI 1240-120

